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Deliverable 5.2

Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications Activities

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SUMMARY

Objective

The main purpose of Deliverable 5.2 is to achieve sustainable, utilizable Bio-Acouis dissemination. Exploitation and communication activities developed by various tools to promote and raise widespread awareness of the project and its results amongst stakeholders. This project report includes the different tools of dissemination and communication activities within know-how methodologies and strategies planning to date as well as the framework of the project.

Rationale

Dissemination and communication activities will be facilitated to promote project results to a variety of audiences. Project coordinator also is leader to implement all these activities within the scope of Work package 5, Deliverables 5.2 (M6). BURO has developed dissemination resources including the project website, project logo, deliverables and presentations templates, project tables, charts etc. All materials and tools will be maintained and updated if necessary, and further resources will be developed over the course of the project in line with the project's Description of Action (DoA) as well as in response to project results and stakeholder requirements. Maximizing the uptake of project results and the overall impact of the project requires effective use of the latest tools, resources and communication channels.

BURO has established key project communication channels, including the project website, social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube), developed dissemination resources including the project logo, templates for deliverables and presentations etc. already stated above. This deliverable report presents an overview of the communication activities that have been carried out since the start of the project, new resources developed since M1 and plans for future communication activities.

CONTENT

SUMMARY	1
CONTENT	2
1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. PROJECT LOGO	3
3. PROJECT WEBSITE	4
4. TEMPLATES	5
5. SOCIAL MEDIA.....	7
6. PROJECT EVENTS	8
7. DISSEMINATION RESOURCES	9
8. INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL E-MAIL GROUP	10
9. CONCLUSION	11

1. INTRODUCTION

Bio-Acouis will be acoustical solution of highly widespread problem while preventing and reducing noises in offices, workplaces, open layout public places, meeting rooms with bio-based materials. The Project focuses on developing acoustic solutions with natural bio-based materials, renewable materials, agricultural wastes etc.

Bio-based materials are ‘sustainable materials’ which have more advantages due to the end of their useful life and easily disposed without damage the environment compared to petroleum or inorganic based materials. Particularly, the bio-based materials are biodegradable, recyclable, renewable, widely available and have a relatively low-cost manufacturing process.

“Communication” is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results to multiple audiences in such a way that they can be understood by non-specialists. The Communications Activities aims to promote the project activities and results, beyond the consortium, to the scientific and research community, industrial stakeholders, policy makers and society, employing a range of communication and dissemination tools.

Dissemination activities and resources commenced with date of the project’s official kick-off. Dissemination activities and resources will be an important element of the project recognition and perception of project with composed of tools on the internet (Project website, Social media channels etc.). Building these resources, project partners have carried out a variety of awareness raising communication activities, including participating in online workshops, conferences and events, producing popularised publications, contributing to a series of news articles for the project website and building a strong presence on social media.

Additional social media channels, namely LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube were established and linked to the project website.

2. PROJECT LOGO

One of the important dissemination action is the project logo which provides first visual impression of project. The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is included in all project promotional material. The Bio-Acouis logo is designed using a combination of Project Name within nature concept such as renewable, eco-friendly, recycled etc. and related with sound wave indications in respect to acoustic features. The project logo also refers to environment and health with use of green in order to reflect the main concept of the Project.

The project logo is available in Google Drive > Common > Project Logo usable for all partner requirements.

Figure 1: Bio-Acouis Logo

3. PROJECT WEBSITE

Bio-Acouis project website is the most important appliance to announce the project and disseminating objectives, work plan and results to a wide audience including all stakeholders and possible end-users. The Bio-Acouis website has been developed following the EU's best practice guidelines for project websites.

To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project's lifetime.

Bio-Acouis website is accessible at: www.bio-acouis.eu.

Figure 2: Bio-Acouis Website

Workpackage 5 leader has developpt visitor counter of the website to track how many people will reach the project results, news, articles etc. by Google Analytics. Analyzing the website visitors will be ensure high level of communication and dissemination plan to comparing within the range of planned audiences. Visitor tracking system is available in the admin panel site dashboard with number of Bio-Acouis website users chart is given below;

Figure 3: Tracking Chart in Site Dashboard

4. TEMPLATES

Project Templates has been developed to promote project results usable in single visual channel from project partners in the scope of dissemination and communication activities. Project templates have visual impressions to internal and external events and meetings and will highlight to project results, project descriptions and events, articles, presentations which are going to be used during the course of the project by all partners.

Templates are designed to visualise the results with green design format, including Project and European Union’s Horizon logos and descriptions. PowerPoint presentation format will be visual tool for internal and external events, workshops, public talks etc. in collaboration with researcher outcomes. Deliverable template (Office word format) is drafted by WP-5 leader in order to be a format for project results, outcomes deliverable reports, will be useful tool for all partners. Project templates are available in Google Drive > Common > Templates to be used for promotion of the Project results by partners. The roll up banners, posters, promotional factsheets, project schematics, brand guidelines, will be developed if needed over the course of the project.

Figure 4: Templates in Google Drive

WP-5 leader has developed the project tracking gantt chart which allows to track deliverable activity progress parallel to the project plan by all partners. The gantt chart is a horizontal bar chart that helps to plan, coordinate and track specific activities in the project. The

horizontal bars with different colours reflect the actual and expected duration and latest status of the actions and tasks. The gantt chart is available on Google Drive with Excel format to use by all partners.

Figure 5: Project Tracking Gantt Chart

5. SOCIAL MEDIA

Social Media is the most effective tool for sharing the project results, events, announcements and all activities regarding Bio-Acouis. All participants need to use this tools to advantage of project in order to promote results and researcher works and share information with academic and non-academic audiences. Social media contents will give readers a look into researchers of project without them having to read and understand journal articles. But in order for these interested readers to find project contents, Bio-Acouis website is the essential part of the dissemination tools. These social media tools provide short and essential information to those who are interested in quick learning, and readers that are interested in ‘diving deeper’ can reach more about the project in the project website.

Twitter

Twitter is one of the favorable social media platform for sharing project research, knowledge, news&events, announcements etc. It is a microblogging system that enables real-

time interaction between followers. All about project news, events, announcements, etc. will be published on Twitter to raise widespread awareness stakeholders. Twitter also will be primary social media channel to aims of disseminations and the knowledges of project reach the people who are interested.

Bio-Acouis Twitter page: [@Bio-Acouis](https://twitter.com/Bio_Acouis) https://twitter.com/Bio_Acouis

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social networking platform that enables users to getting information about project, results, events, media etc. reach other professionals and share information that they find interesting relevant.

Bio-Acouis LinkedIn page: [Bio-Acouis Project | LinkedIn](#)

YouTube

YouTube is also a popular social media network that contributes to dissemination approach of project with video visualization. Through YouTube, project outcomes can disseminate information on various events such as conferences, seminars and workshops are disseminated via YouTube. Project short films will be published to promote at the course of the project on YouTube channel.

Bio-Acouis YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCI9NpFUxBrTgvo0iy6D0gvg>

6. PROJECT EVENTS

The planned project events will be promoted the project results and works to audiences including academic and non-academic stakeholders as well as sharing knowledge and

disseminate with accomplishment to the ultimate destination of project. These events help to ensure that the knowledge generated by the project reaches the target audience and has a significant impact.

The consortium will may achive its goal through the accomplishment of the following objectives workshops, fairs, international conferences, science festivals, etc. These activities are a type of dissemination activity that will be used to enegage stakeholders, share research results, and promote collaboration. Organizing a workshop is a great way to share the results of a Project with stakeholders who may not be familiar with the technical details of the research. By bringing together stakeholders from different backgrounds, researchers will gain valuable insights and feedback that will help to improve Bio-Acouis. Workshops will be arranged to share Project outcomes regarding Work Package WP4 leading by WOOD-K and all partners which will start at M19.

7. DISSEMINATION RESOURCES

Leaflet

The project leaflet was designed by BURO at M5 regarding request from NTT. (The leaflet is given Annex-1) NTT attended ITMA 2023 the fair world's largest international textile and garment technology exhibition. The leaflet provided that promote Bio-Acouis with project description and contact information to audiences. Different format leaflets will be designed to use for events in order to achive same purposes.

Social Media Cards

The project social media cards were desinged by BURO to improve click-through rates.(Cards are given Annex-3) These cards will help increase the visibility of Bio-Acouis by providing a visually appealing and engaging preview when shared on social media.

Roll-up Banner

The project roll-up banner was desinged by BURO marketing team to use for project events, workshops, conferences. Roll-up banner have descriptions about Project partners and

summary of Project aims, goals, results with their large size and vibrant graphics, roll-up banner also have a significant visual impact.

Factsheet

The Project factsheet was designed by BURO marketing team to give a general information of the Bio-Acouis. The factsheet describes the project, its main objectives, approach, solutions, expected results and impact, and consortium.

Project Short Movies/Videos

Videos are the most attractive visual tools to highlight project results regarding the disseminating purposes. Videos and short movies provide a highly engaging visual medium to promote Bio-Acouis. Videos and short movies are also a powerful way to evoke emotions, create a connection with audiences and communicate the core message of Bio-Acouis. After the official period of the project is completed, the video will be produced using the project outputs, will be ensure to reach project videos to audiences all around.

Promotional Articles and Press Releases

Promotional articles and press releases are effective tools for increasing the visibility of the project. By distributing promotional articles and press releases through dissemination channels, such as publication and news&media parts in project website, academic and non-academic websites, social media channels, the project will reach a wider audience and generate interest in Bio-Acouis. All participants are responsible in delivering the bio-acoustics solutions to the public through local and international media. ESRs will collaborate with special press releases and short notes targeted to open blogs of science and social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube etc).

8. INTERNAL AND EXTARNAL MAIL GROUP

Project coordinator also WP-5 leader BURO has developed the one-click mail system with info@bio-acouis.eu address in order to create communication bridge between

stakeholders. This mail system aims to gather together all internal and external communication channels under a single basic way.

If the visitors who has reached the contact information, through other dissemination tools sends an e-mail to project mail address, the e-mail will directly reach all researchers and contact persons or business addresses involved Bio-Acouis.

Audiences who visit the project website, which is one of the important dissemination tools, will be able to reach project results, approach, information about consortium and other outcomes they are looking for about the project through the menus bar.

Visitors can also contact the project authorities and get more information about the Bio-Acouis through the form on the project website, contact page. All messages via the form are sent directly to the project e-mail address, so all accounts connected to this mail can also see there messages.

Figure 6: Contact Page on Project Website

9. CONCLUSION

This report contains the plan of dissemination and communication channels that will enable to share the project outputs, objectives, approach and other related files with the audiences. With these auxiliary tools planned within the scope of WP-5 requirements, the

project aims not only increasing the visibility of the Bio-Acouis but also maximizing the outreach of the generated results. The objective of this report is to provide the Bio-Acouis Consortium with guidelines on how dissemination activities should be performed within the project.

Overall, dissemination plans included in this deliverable are an essential component of Bio-Acouis. These plans help to increase the visibility of the Bio-Acouis, build trust and credibility with stakeholders, increase the impact of the researchs, and encourage further research.

ANNEX 1 – Dissemination Objectives

INDICATOR OF RESULTS	ACTIVITIES
Web-site http://www.bioacouis.eu and web site contents	M2, web site launching

	<p>M6, project summary highlighting the objectives, the contents and the structure of the project including the composition of the consortium partner profiles</p> <p>Weekly, updating, project materials, internal and external communications</p> <p>Provides access to the project’s public deliverables;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications and presentations at external conferences, fairs • Features a news & events section • Communication and contact with the developing community
Dissemination material Newsletters, posters and other	<p>M6, Flyers</p> <p>M12, to convey the project approach and objectives</p> <p>M24, activities and achievement, presentation at conferences, fairs</p> <p>M12, M24, M36 to highlight project achievements</p> <p>M48, final achievements</p>
Workshops	Workshop announcement, contents and flyers, (M12, M22 and M36)
Joint Peer-Reviewed Publications	At least 2 paper publications in peer-reviewed journals, yearly 8 scientific papers will be published
Conferences, fairs	The possible list of the conferences are given in the section
Social media	Regularly on Twitter-Facebook, At least 5 short movie on YouTube
Newspaper articles (Electronic)	At least 2 times newspaper bulletin yearly by Bio-Acouis
jointly developed Horizon Europe or other international proposals	Participation to consortium, project submission (at least 3 proposal)

ANNEX 2 – Social Media Cards

Simple ways to save THE ENVIRONMENT

This project has received funding through the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 101086325 (Bio-Acouis)

Social Media Card

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Social Media Card

MORE THAN
25
RESEARCHERS

BIO-BASED ACOUSTIC SOLUTIONS

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING THROUGH THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2021 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO: 101086325 (BIO-ACOUIS)

bio-acouis

Social Media Cards

Bio-Acouis

*Bio-based solutions for
Improved Acoustic
Applications*

This project has received funding through the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 101086325 (Bio-Acouis)

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ANNEX 2 – Leaflet

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The leaflet features a dark background with a blurred image of mushrooms. It is divided into three vertical sections. The left section has a yellow circle containing a cornfield image, followed by the text 'WE AIM TO REDUCE WASTE AND AVOID POLLUTION.' and a paragraph about noise reduction. The middle section has a yellow envelope icon, the text 'CONTACT US!', and contact information. The right section has a yellow box with a leaf icon, the text 'BIO-BASED ACOUSTIC SOLUTIONS', and a large yellow circle with the 'bio-acouis' logo. Logos for 'BIO' and the European Union are at the bottom.

WE AIM TO REDUCE WASTE AND AVOID POLLUTION.

The project focuses on a highly actual problem of the society and economy, noise is one of the major issue for people who spent most of her time in offices or in the workplace. The demand for acoustic solutions which are cost-effective, renewable, eco-friendly in nature and have a positive impact on human health and well-being.

BIO

 This project has received funding through the European Union's Horizon 2021

CONTACT US!
info@bio-acouis.eu
www.bio-acouis.eu

BIO-BASED ACOUSTIC SOLUTIONS

Leaflet

PROJECT

Bio-Acouis received funding through the European Union's Horizon 2021, innovation project which will provide acoustic solutions made by bio-based materials. The demand for acoustic solutions which are cost-effective, renewable, eco-friendly in nature and have a positive impact on human health and well-being. Bio-Acouis project delivers an improved innovative acoustic solutions based on biobased materials, nanofibers and fully biobased which are biodegradable, lightweight, cost-efficient and eco-friendly in nature while preventing and reducing noises in open plan spaces.

"We are working to create a better future everyday."

4 Countries
Different Areas

8 Partners
Academic and Non-Academic

25 Researcher
Experimentation

48 Months
and more..

 This project has received funding through the European Union's Horizon 2021

Annex 3 – Factsheet

We are working to create a better future everyday!

PROJECT

Noise pollution is a growing problem affecting a growing number of workers in a long list of sectors. Consequently, this increases the demand for cost-effective, renewable, eco-friendly, and positive impact on human health and well-being acoustic solutions. Developing cost-effective natural reproducible materials that contribute to environmental protection is a significant challenge. The EU-funded Bio-Acouis project will deliver innovative and sustainable acoustic solutions based on biobased materials and nanofibers. The project will provide biodegradable, lightweight, cost-efficient and eco-friendly nature solutions which prevent and reduce noise in open-plan office spaces.

OBJECTIVES

The project focuses on a highly actual problem of the society and economy, noise is one of the major issue for people who spent most of her time in offices or in the workplace. The demand for acoustic solutions which are cost-effective, renewable, eco-friendly in nature and have a positive impact on human health and well-being. One of the key strategies and challenges we have is how to develop cost effective natural reproducible materials by combining of the bio-based materials, nanofibers that will contribute to environmental protection and sustainable acoustic solutions that are economic advantages in real world applications than the traditional alternatives.

Factsheet

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KEY ADVANTAGES

Key advantages of Bio-Acoustic approach;

- The most promising process in terms of mechanical strength of the layer and environmental efficiency for the production of final demonstrators.
- Nonfiber technology for performing ultra-thin thickness, ultra-light weight and performing high surface specific area will be layered with electro spun nanofibers as a reinforcement to fabricate acoustic composites
- Bio-based materials – agricultural wastes will be converted into high added value for acoustic solutions

- Natural and cellulose nanofibers will be used for nanofiber production by thermal compression of single and multi-layers structures for acoustic applications.
- Mechanical properties, easy processing, high stability will be leading to high quantity availability, low price, and reduced environmental impacts for their production both in developed countries (increased competitiveness) and developing countries (increase production to provide acoustic solutions)
- Efficient use of resources will be ensured and converting waste materials will be an important contribution to environmental sustainability.
- Ergonomics will be integrated in design with acoustic solutions. It will guide future projects in terms of both material properties and design approaches.

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

CONTACT US

info@bio-acouis.eu
www.bio-acouis.eu

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Document Information

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Bio-based Solutions for Improved Acoustic Applications			
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